

Molecular dynamics simulations of nanoindentation to evaluate the mechanical properties of various metallic alloy nanoparticles

K. Bandyopadhyay^{*}, K.S. Ghosh and M.M. Ghosh

*Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering,
National Institute of Technology, Durgapur – 713209, West Bengal, India*

^{*}Corresponding Author. E-mail: krishnan.bandyopadhyay@gmail.com, (Mobile No.9735603543)

Abstract

We present here the procedure of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of nanoindentation of various metallic alloy nanoparticles viz. copper-silver alloy and copper-nickel alloy with different alloy compositions. The crystals, pre-equilibrated at 298 K are subjected to indentation by spherical shape rigid indenter of specified diameter. For each case we have performed molecular dynamics simulation of a full indentation cycle which includes loading and unloading stages and based on the load-displacement curves we have calculated hardness and Young's modulus of the materials. The Embedded Atom Method (EAM) potential, which is proved to be reliable for metallic systems, has been used here for the interatomic interactions, both during nanoindentation and the prior thermal equilibration stage. During the process of nanoindentation, the resultant load (P) in the nanoparticle has been calculated by summing up the fz component of force of each atom at each time step. The corresponding displacement (h) of the indenter has been calculated taking the centre of mass of the indenter once it touches the nanoparticle's top surface, as the reference. The results indicate the role of surface effect and composition effect in influencing and young's modulus of the alloy nanoparticle. The present work played an evident role for the estimation of mechanical properties of nanoparticles by MD simulations of the nanoindentation process.

Keywords: Molecular dynamics; Nanoindentation; Mechanical properties; Young's modulus; Alloy nanoparticles

References

1. W.C.Oliver et al, J. Mater. Res. 19(2004) 1-18.

Acknowledgment: The financial support of Centre of Excellence under TEQIP-II is thankfully acknowledge